

1 Enhancing the phosphorus content of layered double hydroxide
2 fertilizers by intercalating polymeric phosphate instead of
3 orthophosphate: a feasibility study

4 Supporting Information

5 Maarten Everaert^{1*}, Fien Degryse², Mike J. McLaughlin², Simon Smolders³, Ivan Andelkovic², Erik
6 Smolders¹

7 ¹ Division of Soil and Water Management, Department of Earth and Environmental Science, KU
8 Leuven, Kasteelpark Arenberg 20, B-3001 Heverlee, Belgium.

9 ² School of Agriculture, Food and Wine, The University of Adelaide, PMB 1, Waite Campus, Glen
10 Osmond, SA 5064, Australia.

11 ³ Centre for Membrane Separations, Adsorption, Catalysis and Spectroscopy for Sustainable
12 Solutions (cMACS), KU Leuven, Celestijnenlaan 200F, 3001 Leuven, Belgium.

13 * Corresponding author: maarten.everaert@kuleuven.be

14

15 Figure S1: The XRD patterns of the as-synthesized Mg_2Al , Mg_3Al and Mg_4Al LDHs.

16

17 Figure S2: The initial (prior to LDH addition) and final pH of the exchange solutions of the Mg₂Al, Mg₃Al or Mg₄Al LDH,
 18 presented as function of the amount of orthophosphate (PO₄) or trimetaphosphate (P₃O₉) added to the exchange solutions
 19 relative the AEC. Error bars represent the standard error (n=2).

20

21 Figure S3: Intramolecular distances of the trimetaphosphate (P_3O_9) anion, with values in Å.

22

Table S1: Weight loss of Mg₂Al and Mg₃Al LDHs during calcination treatments.

	300°C	350°C	400°C	450°C	500°C
Mg ₂ Al	19.6%	31.8%	37.2%	39.6%	40.9%
Mg ₃ Al	21.2%	34.6%	38.2%	40.6%	41.3%

23

24

25 Figure S4: The final pH of the PO₄ and P₃O₉ exchange solutions in the presence of Mg₂Al or Mg₃Al, either in as-synthesized
 26 (AS) or calcinated form.

27

28 Figure S5: The release of P from $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Na}_3\text{P}_3\text{O}_9$, either or not loaded into a dialysis membrane, incubated in a
 29 2 M NaHCO_3 solution and measured either as TP (ICP-OES analysis) or as MRP (spectrophotometric analysis), presented as a
 30 function of the incubation time. Error bars represent the standard error (n=2).

31

Table S2: Final pH of the external desorption solution, reported with standard error (n=2).

	Final pH of external solution
Control	8.33 ± 0.01
NaH ₂ PO ₄	8.35 ± 0.02
NaH ₂ PO ₄ (REF)	8.41 ± 0.01
Na ₃ P ₃ O ₉	8.40 ± 0.01
Na ₃ P ₃ O ₉ (REF)	8.43 ± 0.01
PO ₄ -Mg ₂ Al LDH	8.39 ± 0.01
P ₃ O ₉ -Mg ₂ Al LDH	8.38 ± 0.02
PO ₄ -Mg ₃ Al LDH	8.47 ± 0.01
P ₃ O ₉ -Mg ₃ Al LDH	8.55 ± 0.05

32

33

34 Figure S6: The pH values of the CaCl₂ soil extracts presented as a function of the incubation time. The soils were incubated
 35 with soluble P compounds (NaH₂PO₄, Na₃P₃O₉, KH₂PO₄), LDH-P compounds (PO₄-Mg₃Al LDH, P₃O₉-Mg₃Al LDH), or without
 36 added P (control). Error bars represent the standard error (n=3).